

Electroencephalogram: Code of Soul

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Abstract

Bioelectricity is the basic feature of life activities. Our brain produces brain waves all the time. Theoretically, brain waves should never disappear, and will always "float" in the universe. Brain wave is a kind of biological electromagnetic wave, which should be the carrier of mind, consciousness or soul. Its material basis is human body, brain, brain cells and ions inside and outside cells. It can be seen that the ancients said that there are gods three feet above the ground, as well as the so-called reincarnation, reincarnation, telepathy, and karma, there is a certain scientific reason.

Keywords: Electroencephalogram ; telepathy; Code of Soul

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Bioelectricity is the basic feature of life activities. The word cell in English has the meaning of battery, and each brain cell is a tiny power station. Our brain produces brain waves all the time. Brain waves are some spontaneous rhythmic neural electrical activities. Their frequency ranges from 1 to 30 times / s, including four bands, namely $\alpha\beta\theta\delta$. Among α The rhythm is 8 ~ 13 Hz, with an average of 10 times / second. It is the basic rhythm of normal brain waves. When people are awake and meditating, α The rhythm is most obvious. When you open your eyes or receive other stimuli, α The wave disappears instantly. When people are happy or meditate, α The wave was enhanced, which was closest to the EEG biological rhythm of the right brain.

Brain wave is a kind of weak biological electromagnetic wave. The propagation speed of electromagnetic wave is equal to the speed of light, which is 300000 km / s. The propagation of light from the sun to the earth takes 8.3 minutes. China's Sky Survey Telescope (FAST) can see through an area of 13.7 billion light-years and walk alone in the world with the magic of a thousand years at a glance. In other words, when our Sky Survey Telescope receives signals from a star 13.7 billion light-years away, the star may not be in its original position, or it may no longer exist.

Because of this, theoretically, brain waves should never disappear, and will always "float" in the universe, that is, people are no longer alive, but their brain waves are still there. We can imagine our brain as an electrical signal receiver, which is equivalent to a radio, television or mobile phone. When one of our brain waves happens to have the same frequency as the brain waves "floating" in the air, or on the same channel, we will receive this signal. So, is there a certain scientific truth about the ancient saying that there are gods three feet away from the ground, and the so-called reincarnation, reincarnation, telepathy and karma?

Mind acts upon mind. Most of us may have had such an experience. When our relatives are thousands of miles away, if major changes happen, we have more or less had such telepathy. We have abnormal emotions during the day and strange dreams at night. How can this be explained? It is hard to say whether there is a soul in this world. We cannot detect brain waves in the air, which does not mean that brain waves do not exist. That is because our human science and technology are not developed enough, and the accuracy of detection instruments is not enough.

We humans are realizing the interconnection of all things. Under big data, there is no secret. Everyone knows what you do. But I tell you, if one day, everyone else knows what you think, what will you think? Is fine thinking very afraid? Would you believe that human technology allows you to think what you think and control what you do? Believe it or not, when the day comes, no one gives you advance warning.

Brain wave is a kind of biological electromagnetic wave, which should be the carrier of mind, consciousness or soul. Its material basis is human body, brain, brain cells and ions inside and outside cells. Brain wave has been well applied in basic theory research of brain science, clinical practice of medicine, artificial intelligence and other fields. In 2020, American scientists

translated human brain waves into English, with an accuracy rate of 97%. Mind reading has become possible. In the future, brain waves can also be used to crack the secrets of all living animals and plants, such as understanding the language of birds, reading the mind of flowers, and talking to animals and plants. Therefore, brain waves are the golden key to crack the human soul code. The brainwave of each of us, like the human genetic code, should belong to personal privacy and must be protected in advance. It cannot be easily extracted or collected by others, nor can it be used by people or countries with ulterior motives.